

Driver Distraction Detection and Evaluation with Artificial Neural Network and Fuzzy Logic

In-vehicle information system as a driver's secondary activity: Case study

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Abstract— A robust methodology for detecting and evaluating driver distraction induced by in-vehicle information system using artificial neural network and fuzzy logic is introduced in this paper. An artificial neural network is used to predict driver's performance on a specific road segment. The predicted performance-based measures are compared to the driving with secondary task accomplishment. Fuzzy logic is applied to fuse the variables into a single output, which constitutes a level of driver distraction in percentage. The technique was tested on a vehicle simulator by ten drivers that exploited in-vehicle information system as a secondary activity. The driver-in-the-loop experiment outcomes are discussed.

Keywords—artificial neural networks; fuzzy logic; vehicle safety; machine learning; prediction methods

I. INTRODUCTION

Driver distraction (DD) causes serious environmental problem every year. Not to mention injuries, DD contributes to more than 5000 traffic fatalities yearly in the USA alone. Unfortunately, this trend does not tend to decline [1].

DD is defined as "anything that delays the recognition of information necessary to safety maintain the lateral and longitudinal control of the vehicle (driver's primary task) due to some event, activity, object or person, within or outside the vehicle that compels or tends to induce the driver's shifting attention away from the fundamental driving task by compromising the driver's auditory, biomechanical, cognitive or visual faculties or combinations thereof". The activities not related to primary tasks driver perform while driving are defined as secondary activities [2, 3, 4, 5].

There are two types of secondary tasks: interaction with in-vehicle information system (IVIS) (e.g. controlling comfort and entertainment), and interaction with the items brought to a vehicle (e.g. portable electronic devices, passengers, pets) [2]. DD minimization caused by IVIS is under vehicle manufacturers' responsibility. In particular, the vehicle cockpit and human-machine interface (HMI) must be safe for operation, intuitive, well organized, and, what is most important, not distract a driver from her/his primary task.

Development of a robust DD detection and assessment methodology while interacting with IVIS allows testing different HMI technologies and cockpit designs before they are accepted in series vehicle. DD evaluation is also applied in advanced driver assistance systems impact on driver's situation awareness. Today, there are still no accurate evaluation technologies for DD induced by IVIS [2, 6, 7].

Previously, many different attributes were proposed for DD detection. Among them, psychological [8], behavioral [9], subjective [10], performance-based or their combinations [11] are known. For DD detection, machine learning (e.g. support vector machine, graph-regularized extreme learning machine, k -nearest neighbor) deserved special attention among other algorithms [12].

Artificial neural network (ANN) is one of the most popular machine learning approaches [13] due to its robustness, ability to learn by example, and efficiency in intelligent systems. The ANNs are used in various disciplines: physics, statistics, psychology, cognitive science, neuroscience, and linguistics, not to mention computer science, electrical engineering, and adaptive control [14]. Many researchers on DD detection and assessment applied ANN to solve their problems.

In [15], a three-dimensional convolutional neural network (CNN) and gradient boosting algorithms combination were proposed for drowsiness classification. Gaze zone categorization was designed using CNN in [16]. A probabilistic restricted Coulomb energy ANN was implemented for drowsy driving prediction in [17]. In these works, the researchers preferred behavioral attributes. Unfortunately, behavioral and psychological attributes always require supplementary devices (e.g. cameras and neuro-scan systems) that increase system cost and complexity [18].

Another famous approach of DD detection - performance-based - does not require additional devices. These methods depend on vehicle dynamic performance, which is tracked by the sensors available in modern vehicles (e.g. vehicle velocity and steering wheel angle). In [19], the scholars proposed DD detection using in-vehicle signals without planned distraction. The machine learning schemes, ANN, and Gaussian mixture

models were combined to solve the problem. In [20], a real-time DD detection classifier using vehicle dynamic data was introduced. Different machine learning algorithms, including static and dynamic ANNs, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system, and support vector machine, were compared. The last one outperformed all the other classifiers.

For accurate DD detection, different attributes can be combined. For example, behavioral (i.e. head movement) and performance-based data were integrated for the online DD detection with long- and short-term memory recurrent ANN in [21]. In [22], an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system for DD prediction was developed. This approach showed better performance comparing to the ANN and radial basic function prediction algorithms.

Another computational intelligence method, fuzzy logic (FL), is also widely used in automotive engineering, from vehicle dynamics control [23] to DD evaluation [24]. A thorough review on fuzzy methods in automotive engineering applications can be found in [25].

Although the results of the related works were very positive in DD detection, they all use the 2-class classification: distracted or not distracted. This classification is not suitable for measuring the DD level and consequent IVIS HMI technology comparative evaluation. Hence, in this paper a solution of the regression problem is proposed for DD detection with performance-based attributes bearing in mind that ANNs are actively used for nonlinear regression [14].

An ANN is designed as a driver performance predictor in a name of lane keeping ability and speed limit maintenance. First, the ANN is trained with data collected during the DD-free driving. Next, the predicted variables are compared to the same variables collected during driver's run with completing secondary task in parallel to driving. The comparison is used for DD detection. As FL is efficient in data fusion [26, 27], it is applied to merge vehicle dynamics into a single variable. This variable depicts a level of DD in percentage caused by a secondary activity.

Next Section is dedicated to the methodology based on ANN and FL combination description. The driver-in-the-loop experiment was conducted on an advanced driving simulator provided by ŠKODA AUTO (Mladá Boleslav, Czech Republic). The experiment procedure, subjects, and apparatus are described in Section III. The DD detection and evaluation methodology outcomes are stressed in Section IV. Finally, the research conclusion is provided in Section V.

II. DRIVER DISTRACTION DETECTION METHOD

The block scheme of the DD detection and evaluation method is presented in Fig. 1. The symbols' description and annotation are introduced in Table I. The method involves three steps. First, the ANN predicts a vehicle dynamic performance on a specific road segment taking as the inputs an information about the road segment: speed limit V_l and curvature (radius) r . The outputs of the ANN describe predicted driver performance on a specific road segment: ability to hold a speed limit Δv_p and to stay in the middle of the road lane Δx_p . The training data for the ANN are collected

Fig. 1. DD detection and evaluation method block scheme.

during the first phase of the experiment, when the driver demonstrates her/his normal vehicle operation, without secondary activity.

Second, the predicted variables are compared to a real driving performance Δx and Δv with IVIS interaction. The comparison outcomes are the resultative variables Δx_r and Δv_r , calculated using the following rules:

$$\Delta x_r = \begin{cases} \Delta x - \Delta x_p, & \text{if } \Delta x > 0; \Delta x_p > 0; |\Delta x| > |\Delta x_p| \\ \Delta x - \Delta x_p, & \text{if } \Delta x < 0; \Delta x_p < 0; |\Delta x| > |\Delta x_p| \\ \Delta x + \Delta x_p, & \text{if } \Delta x > 0; \Delta x_p < 0; |\Delta x| > |\Delta x_p| \\ \Delta x + \Delta x_p, & \text{if } \Delta x < 0; \Delta x_p > 0; |\Delta x| > |\Delta x_p| \\ 0, & \text{if } |\Delta x| \leq |\Delta x_p| \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta v_r = \begin{cases} \Delta v - \Delta v_p, & \text{if } \Delta v > 0; \Delta v_p > 0; |\Delta v| > |\Delta v_p| \\ \Delta v - \Delta v_p, & \text{if } \Delta v < 0; \Delta v_p < 0; |\Delta v| > |\Delta v_p| \\ \Delta v + \Delta v_p, & \text{if } \Delta v > 0; \Delta v_p < 0; |\Delta v| > |\Delta v_p| \\ \Delta v + \Delta v_p, & \text{if } \Delta v < 0; \Delta v_p > 0; |\Delta v| > |\Delta v_p| \\ 0, & \text{if } |\Delta v| \leq |\Delta v_p| \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Negative Δx means that the vehicle drives closer to the road dividing line. Contrariwise, positive Δx means that the vehicle drives towards off road from the middle of the lane. Negative Δv shows that the vehicle velocity is lower than the speed limit on a road segment whereas positive Δv signifies speeding. Finally, FL completes data fusion and outputs a level of DD in percentage DD .

The evaluation method is programmed in MATLAB[®] (Natick, MA, USA) environment. The Neural Network Toolbox[™] was exploited for the design of the ANN driver performance predictor. One of the most popular methods due to its optimal computation complexity - backpropagation [13] -

TABLE I. PARAMETERS DESCRIPTION

Symbol	Description	Unit
r	Road radius	m
V_l	Speed limit	km/h
Δx	Real lane keeping offset	m
Δv	Real vehicle speed deviation	km/h
Δx_p	Predicted lane keeping offset	m
Δv_p	Predicted vehicle speed deviation	km/h
Δx_r	Resultative lane keeping offset	m
Δv_r	Resultative vehicle speed deviation	km/h
DD	Driver distraction in percentage	%

TABLE II. RULE-BASE OF THE FL EVALUATOR

DD [%]		Δx_r [m]				
		very close	close	zero	far	very far
Δv_r [km/h]	very low	100	71.5	42.9	71.5	100
	low	85.8	14.3	0	14.3	85.8
	zero	42.9	0	0	0	42.9
	high	71.5	14.3	0	14.3	71.5
	very high	85.8	57.2	28.6	57.2	85.5

was used for computing gradients in the ANN. The algorithm detailed description for training a multilayer perceptron for regression is reported in [14].

The Levenberg-Marquardt method is the most suitable for training an ANN with nonlinear regression (function fitting) purposes. In practice, ANNs incorporate three and sometimes four layers, including one or two hidden layers with 10 to 1000 neurons in each. More hidden layers do not guarantee better ANN performance likewise the greater number of neurons does. On the contrary, each additional layer increases the computational burden exponentially [14, 15].

Two hidden layers were used for ANN in this study. The network performance was tested on different number of neurons in each layer. However, we did not notice the ANN significant enhancement with more than 100 neurons. Due to its simplicity and superior performance [13], the tangent-sigmoid activation function was applied in the hidden layers. As a rule, for the outputs the linear transfer functions are used in regression [13]. In short, a feedforward ANN with two hidden layers of 100 neurons each, with a tangent-sigmoid transfer function in the hidden layer, and a linear transfer function in the output layer was designed using the Levenberg-Marquardt training method.

In this research, an FL Sugeno's type inference mechanism based on simple matrix operations suitable for C, C++, MATLAB® script, and other programming languages was used [24]. The FL DD evaluator has a "2 inputs - 1 output" structure. The inputs are Δx_r and Δv_r . The DD output represents a level of DD in percentage (Fig. 1).

Five symmetrically dispersed and overlapped over the whole universe of discourse (UOD) triangular membership functions (MFs) capable for fast response and easy for

Fig. 2. The DD FL evaluator nonlinear control surface.

programming were designed for both inputs. Inputs' equal sensitivity is guaranteed by the symmetric MFs dispersion. The Δx_r UOD was bounded between [-1.5, 1.5] whereas the Δv_r UOD was narrowed in [-12, 12].

The output UOD is bounded within [0, 100]. The output MFs represent eight singletons with equal step 14.3 between each other: {0, 14.3, 28.6, 42.9, 57.2, 71.5, 85.8, 100}. The step is calculated by dividing the highest value of UOD boundary by an amount of MFs starting from the second singleton, because the first one is equal to zero. Consequently, the fixed step between the output MFs guarantees their equal sensitivity inside of the UOD.

Modus-ponens-form rules "If-Then" are applied to connect the inputs with the output. The input-output linguistic relation is presented in Table II. The control surface for the designed FL evaluator is shown in Fig. 2. An example of the linguistic input-output mapping is performed as follows:

IF the vehicle center is "far" from the road dividing line **AND** driver's speed is "low" comparing to the road speed limit, **THEN** driver distraction is "14.3%".

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Subjects

Ten driver-in-the-loop experiment participants were members of the Interdisciplinary Training Network in Multi-Actuated Ground Vehicles (ITEAM) project. In this study, only male drivers participated. Their age ranged between 27 and 31 years old. Every participant owned a valid driver license. All drivers took part in the experiment voluntarily.

The experiment participation was not paid. However, for their contribution the participants were awarded with a guided tour to ŠKODA AUTO museum and vehicle production plant (Mladá Boleslav, Czech Republic) free of charge.

B. Apparatus

The experiment was conducted on available in ŠKODA AUTO HMI laboratory (Mladá Boleslav, Czech Republic) facilities that consist of a fixed-base vehicle mockup and a wall screen in front of the driver, where the virtual world is projected (Fig. 3). A driver settled down inside the vehicle simulator, which has an automatic gearbox, steering wheel, adjustable driver's seat, acceleration and brake pedals. The

Fig. 3. Driver-in-the-loop experiment facility.

TABLE III. IN-VEHICLE SECONDARY TASKS

#	In-vehicle secondary task	
1.	Volume	Volume regulation
2.	Context selection	Radio
3.		Media
4.		Telephone
5.		Navigation
6.	Radio	Radio station selection from a primary list
7.		Radio station selection from an overall list
8.	Media	Media source selection (e.g. CD, SD-card)
9.		Media item selection
10.		Song shuffle
11.	Telephone	Call a number from a favorite contact list
12.		Call a number from an overall contact list
13.	Navigation	Input location
14.		Input of a next target
15.		Zoom operation

vehicle cockpit is identical to the one used in commercial vehicles. The simulator's head-up instrument panel displays current vehicle velocity. All the secondary tasks are conducted via the HMI display placed, like in most of the European countries, on the driver's right.

Vehicle dynamics and virtual world are modelled using an open source library for simulating rigid body dynamics Open Dynamics Engine™ v 0.5 in C++ programming language [28]. The vehicle model consists of the vehicle body, suspension system, four wheels, and the tire model completed with Pacejka's Magic Formula [29]. The vehicle is parametrized according to Škoda Yeti SK316 with 1.4 liters twincharged stratified injection 77 kW engine specifications. The drivers could understand when they drive off the road on a grass by the screen vibration. However, they could not feel crossing the road dividing line.

Three coordinates (i.e. x, y, z) are saved in the virtual world for each wheel with 0.1 seconds sample period. These data are exploited for lane keeping offset and for vehicle speed deviation calculations. The drivers control the vehicle via the steering wheel and the brake and acceleration pedals.

C. Procedure

The driver-in-the-loop experiment participants were asked to drive the two-way lap of a total length of 10626 meters with a 3.5 meters width lane. The road has two main segments: the curvy road with a speed limit of 50 km/h and the almost straight road with slight curvature of 90 km/h. When all the speed limits are respected, one lap takes approximately 10 minutes for driving. There were no other traffic participants modelled, neither pedestrians nor other vehicles.

To familiarize with the simulator, the drivers were allowed to drive it unlimited time, before the start of the driver-in-the-loop experiment. Thus, they were aware of the test rig and the road shape preliminary. What is more, the participants were instructed to the studied HMI display. They could try all the secondary tasks in advance.

The experiment for each participant was divided into two parts. First, the drivers were asked to pass two laps showing their best performance in lane keeping ability and following all the traffic regulations (i.e. speed limits). They were not fulfilling a secondary activity during the first part of the experiment. The data collected during the free from the secondary task driving were used for the ANN training. During the second part, the drivers were asked to continue driving obeying the traffic rules and staying in the middle of the lane as good as feasible. However, this time they drove the same road performing a secondary activity in parallel. The participants

Fig. 4. Driver performance prediction versus real driver performance example for one of the experiment participants: gray background — the secondary task accomplishment period; red line — real driver performance; black line — predicted performance; green line — road information; (a) speed difference Δv and road speed limit V_i ; (b) center lane keeping offset Δx and road radius r .

were allowed to take a break between the experiment parts.

The in-vehicle secondary tasks are introduced in Table III. The experiment organizer sent the vocal command to the driver for a secondary activity request. When the secondary task is accomplished, the driver sent a feedback to the experimenter via a switch around the steering wheel. If the task is correct, the driver heard a vocal signal informing that the submitted task is correct. If the completed task is wrong and the driver did not hear the sound signal, she/he had to perform the secondary activity again. The participant had a reasonable time between each secondary task request. No time restriction for a secondary task realization was applied.

IV. RESULTS

The driver-in-the-loop experiment outcomes are presented in this section. A random driver performance prediction, DD detection and evaluation with FL is studied here in details. For the rest of the participants the results are very similar: low DD during normal driving and high level of *DD* while performing a secondary activity.

In Fig. 4, the driver performance prediction for Δv_p and Δx_p versus real performance Δv and Δx with secondary activity is introduced. During the experiment, the driver passed more than two full laps. However, in this paper the results only from the last lap are presented.

Within normal driving, the driver tended to keep the speed slightly lower its road segment limit (Fig 4a; black curve). In average, the speed deviation did not exceed 5 km/h. When the secondary task is performed (Fig. 4a; red curve), the speed limit maintenance ability has higher oscillation. For example, in the period from 820 s to 900 s the driver slowed the speed by more than 25 km/h, while during the DD-free run the participant was able to keep Δv almost at zero.

The lane keeping ability along with road radiuses are introduced in Fig. 4b. In average, the participant was holding

the middle line with 0.2 m error. On the contrary, when the driver was performing a secondary activity, his driving performance was significantly burdened. The lane keeping ability lower than -1 m or higher than 1 m means that the vehicle was driving out of the road bounds. When the participant performed secondary tasks, in most of the cases the vehicle went outside the road limits.

As it is noticed in Fig. 4, the interaction with the IVIS influences the vehicle dynamic performance. The impact depends on a task complexity. The proposed DD detection method easily recognizes the difference between normal DD-free driving and driving while performing the secondary task. Thereafter, the FL evaluates the level of DD.

In Fig. 5, DD evaluation is presented. It is seen that *DD* is noticeably higher when the driver interacts with HMI by executing the secondary activity. For some tasks (Table III), the *DD* is low, for example, in case of the task number 1 - volume regulation. On the contrary, some tasks caused very high *DD*. For instance, with the task number 13 - searching for a new location in a navigation system, the driver performed badly for a quite long period (Fig. 5, inset). It can also be observed from Fig. 4 for the period between 820 s and 900 s. During this secondary task accomplishment, the driver dropped the speed and went off the road several times (Fig. 4). The method easily detects these mistakes in vehicle dynamic performance and provides an appropriate evaluation (Fig. 5).

V. CONCLUSION

A DD detection and evaluation method based on ANN and FL combination is presented in this paper. An ANN is applied to solve a regression problem in driver performance prediction on a specific road segment. The prediction is based on normal driving without performing a secondary activity. Next, the predicted performance-based variables are compared to the same vehicle dynamics data collected during the driver run with secondary activity accomplishment. The performance

Fig. 5. Driver distraction evaluation results: gray background — the secondary task accomplishment period; blue curve — DD. The secondary task number refers to Table III.

degradation is accepted as a DD detection. Finally, the data pass through FL evaluator, which outputs a level of DD.

The method is verified in driver-in-the-loop experiment on an advanced driver decoy simulator with ten participants. The results show that the methodology is always capable to detect DD when an experiment participant interacts with IVIS. The evaluation by FL allows an accurate comparison of different in-vehicle secondary tasks. In particular, it shows what secondary tasks lead to higher level of DD comparing to another ones. The proposed methodology provides a practical tool for HMI technologies comparative analysis.

In the future, more driver-in-the-loop participants will be studied on IVIS-induced DD detection and evaluation with the proposed methodology. Moreover, other machine learning algorithms (e.g. k -nearest neighbor, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system, and long short-term memory) efficient in nonlinear regression [14] will be applied and compared to an ANN. Different attributes combination and more performance-based variables will be used for the method improvement.

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